

Parachor of Benzaldehydes and Acetophenones

S. H. Dandekar and S. G. Shet

The parachors of substituted benzaldehydes and acetophenones have been measured in benzene and methanol and the validity of Hammick and Andrew's equation is confirmed. A simplified procedure for the preparation of nitrohydroxybenzaldehydes is reported.

Hammick and Andrew¹ calculated parachors for a number of solutes in the solvents, assuming the parachors obeying the straight-line mixture law:

$$P_m = P(1 - x) + P_x x$$

where P_m is the parachor of the mixture, P , that of the pure solvent, P_x , that of the solute, and x , the molar fraction of the solute. It was also stated that the parachor increased proportionately with the concentration of the solution. Despite Hammick and Andrew's observations¹, Kaveeshwar and Dwivedi² observed that in the solution containing the molar fraction up to 0.9 mole of solute, there was scarcely any change in the parachor with concentration, but with higher molar fraction a slight increase in the value was noticed, due probably to the solvent molecules being too few for the formation of hydrogen bond.

Ray³ and Bhagwat *et al.*⁴ stated that the parachor values of the solutes, determined in different solvents, agreed very closely, with a few exceptions, with the values either calculated or determined in the fused state. The agreement is most complete, generally, in a very dilute solution. The studies on parachor have been extended for the determination of resonance structures and hydrogen bond.

Lutakii⁵ emphasised the ability of phenols to utilise the halogen atom in *ortho* position to form an intramolecular hydrogen bond, but this bond appeared to him to be weak compared with the one formed between hydrogen of hydroxyl group and carbonyl group in *ortho* position in benzaldehyde or acetophenone. From the studies of temperature effect⁶ on hydrogen bonding, Buehler *et al.*⁶ found no change in parachor values occurring with variations in temperature for intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded compounds, but their isomers showed considerable variations.

In the present communication the studies on parachor of benzaldehydes and acetophenones are reported in ionic and nonionic solvents as only aliphatic carbonyl compounds

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754.
2. *Agr. Univ. J. Res. (Science)*, 1957, 6, 39.
3. *This Journal*, 1934, 11, 671.
4. Bhagwat *et al.*, *Agr. Univ. J. Res.*, 1955, 4, 1; *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 679.
5. *Zhur. Fiz. Khim.*, 1952, 29, 1162; *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1954, 24, 240; 1955, 25, 1086.
6. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 2, 187.

have been earlier studied in solvents⁴ except one case⁷. The compounds need to be extremely pure to obtain satisfactory results. The compounds having an intramolecular hydrogen bonding show anticipated results both in benzene and methanol solutions. The determination of values in benzene show the decrease of 14-20 units for intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded compounds and 7-10 units per associated bond in methanol. In the former case it could be attributed to hydrogen bonding, whereas in the latter the hydrogen bond is ruptured⁵ to provide carbonyl group, which would associate with the solvent, and causes fall in parachor values of 7-10 units per associated bond. The results are in excellent agreement with the findings of Kaveeshwar and Dwivedi⁴. These associated compounds show normal behaviour in benzene. Similarly, the low values for the density⁸ and surface tension⁵ for intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded compounds, compared with associated compounds, substantiate the above findings. 3-Nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde shows typical behaviour where nitro group, instead of carbonyl group, is involved in the formation of hydrogen bond and thus fall in parachor is considerably more. The hydrogen bond between oxygen of nitro group and hydrogen of hydroxyl group is very strong and this has been confirmed by Lewis *et al.*⁹ from the studies of reaction kinetics. 2-Hydroxybenzaldehydes and 2-hydroxyacetophenones, having halogen substituent in *ortho* position to hydroxyl group, would tend to form hydrogen bond, whereas the halogen does not seem to have any effect on the same. Lutskii⁵ has stated that the five-membered chelate ring, formed from hydrogen of hydroxyl group and halogen in *ortho* position, is weak compared with the six-membered chelate ring formed by hydrogen of hydroxyl group and *ortho*-substituted carbonyl group.

The small variations found for parachor values in a few cases may be attributed to the Gibbs surface absorption effect. The observed values of the parachor are less than those calculated, using Sugden's atomic and structural parachor¹⁰, but the extent of this diminution could not be used to distinguish between strong and weak hydrogen bond similar to IR absorption measurements¹¹. The studies are helpful to determine intramolecular hydrogen bond, associated bond, and resonance structures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The aldehydes and acetophenones were prepared by known procedures and purified until the constant m.p. attained. The commercially available compounds were recrystallised or redistilled before use. The surface tension was measured thrice for each solution and the two coinciding values were used for calculation, using Hammick and Andrew's equations for solutions¹. The results are recorded in Tables I and II.

7. Khandekar and Bhagwat, *Agra. Univ. J. Res.*, 1957, 6, 53.

8. Pimental and McClellan, "The Hydrogen Bond", W. H. Freeman & Co., London, 1960, p. 199.

9. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1945, 10, 145.

10. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1177.

11. Pimohas, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29, 334; 1955, 27, 2; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 1862; *Chem. & Ind.*, 1959, 1457.

12. *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1928.

TABLE I
Parachor values for benzaldehydes.

No.	Benzaldehydes.	In benzene.			In methanol.			P ₂ .	P ₃ .	Calc. value.				
		z.	M _m .	γ.	z.	M _m .	γ.							
1	2-Hydroxy.	0.200	86.8	0.9122	27.95	218.2	287	0.200	50.00	0.8766	28.18	129.80	297	276.1
2	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-	0.200	93.7	0.9705	29.86	225.6	304	0.100	44.45	0.8813	22.14	109.40	302	312.3
3	2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-	0.200	107.6	1.0890	28.31	226.2	217	..	..	..	..	..	..	336.0
4	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dibromo-	0.100	98.2	1.0380	29.88	222.3	269	0.100	56.80	1.0680	22.40	116.00	368	378.9
5	2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-	0.200	93.7	0.9870	28.58	226.0	306	0.1316	48.40	0.9066	22.61	116.43	304	312.3
6	2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-	0.100	90.2	0.9596	28.43	217.3	319	0.100	48.90	0.9457	22.19	111.20	320	320.0
7	2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-	0.200	94.8	0.9834	28.40	226.6	324	0.200	59.00	0.9768	22.79	123.00	308	331.1
8	2-Hydroxy-5-nitro-	0.200	94.8	0.9828	28.13	226.2	322	..	..	..	..	..	..	331.1
9	2-Nitro-	0.200	92.6	0.9428	28.62	227.2	312	0.200	55.80	0.9500	22.28	127.60	286	311.0
10	2-Chloro-	0.200	90.5	0.9876	28.42	222.8	290	0.200	53.70	0.9264	22.16	125.80	277	292.3
11	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	0.200	99.6	0.9768	28.26	224.8	350	0.100	47.25	0.9279	22.49	111.20	320	248.0
12	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	0.100	93.2	0.9690	28.03	221.4	320	0.100	61.90	1.0043	22.82	112.70	286	261.9
13	4-Bromo-	0.200	99.4	1.0070	27.64	226.4	308	0.200	62.80	1.0810	22.54	129.80	297	306.0
14	2,4-Dibromo-	0.200	116.2	1.1280	28.24	225.6	254	0.040	41.27	0.9149	22.72	98.48	350	369.9

See Table No. 2.

TABLE II
Parachor values for acetophenones.

No.	Acetophenones.	In benzene.			In methanol.			P ₂ .	P ₃ .	Calc. value.				
		z.	M _m .	γ.	z.	M _m .	γ.							
1	2-Hydroxy-4-chloro-	0.200	97.5	0.9728	29.02	223.4	249	0.200	60.70	0.9554	22.25	127.20	324	341.3
2	2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-	0.200	106.4	1.0820	28.47	225.8	255	0.160	59.45	1.0080	22.11	128.50	358	365.0
3	4-Hydroxy-5-chloro-	..	..	..	..	..	..	0.200	59.70	0.9432	22.08	126.40	240	261.2
4	4-Hydroxy-5-bromo-	0.200	106.4	0.9500	31.20	227.4	263	0.0465	40.48	0.8790	22.21	100.20	301	265.0
5	2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-	0.200	97.5	0.9648	28.61	224.0	246	0.200	60.70	0.9619	22.21	128.40	240	261.2
6	2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-	0.200	106.4	1.0240	27.71	226.0	266	0.1784	64.71	0.9879	21.85	129.44	356	368.0

N. B. Value for chlorate ring 6-10 units to be added.

2-Hydroxy-3-nitro- and 2-hydroxy-5-nitro-benzaldehydes were obtained by Miller's process, simplified as follows:

Fuming nitric acid (15.5 ml) was added dropwise over an hour to a well-stirred ice-cold solution of salicylaldehyde (12.2 g.) in acetic acid (75 ml) and stirring continued for 2 hr. at 0°. The mixture on being allowed to attain the room temperature, a yellow precipitate separating was dissolved on warming at 45-50° for 45 min. and was set aside.

2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzaldehyde (5.0 g., 35.8%; m.p. 126-27°) separating as stout yellow needles was filtered, washed with acetic acid, and dried. The filtrate on dilution with water afforded a mixture of nitrosalicylaldehydes (m. p. 84-90°), which on crystallisation from ethanol furnished 3-nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (4.5 g., 27.77%), m.p. 110-11°.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
KARNATAK UNIVERSITY,
DHARWAD.

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